

Support to the Activities of the
Concentrated Solar Thermal
Technology Area of the SET Plan

September 23-26, 2025
Almeria, Spain
31st SolarPACES Conference

SIDE EVENT: EU CST PROJECTS & RESEARCH AGENDA

Date and time	25 th September, 2025 8:30 – 10:30 CEST
Hybrid event	Physical at SolarPACES Conference Room 7 Online via Teams
Registration	Free registration for online participants here

This event is organized in the framework of the CST4ALL project, and focuses on EU-funded research in Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) and how these projects contribute to fulfilling the CST Implementation Plan of the SET-Plan.

The workshop will feature several EU-supported CST projects, which will present their objectives, main results, and perspectives on future developments. It will conclude with a round-table discussion on EU funding and future research requirements to meet the goals of the CST Implementation Plan.

Agenda

8:30	Introduction & EU-funded CST projects overview Daniel Benitez, DLR
8:40	MSA-Trough project Diogo Canavarro, University of Evora
8:55	ASTERIx-CAESar project Fritz Zaversky, Cener
9:10	Sun-to-Liquid II project José González-Aguilar, IMDEA Energy
9:25	SolarSCO2OL & SHARP-sCO2 projects Rafael Guedez, KTH
9:40	SALTOPower project Radia Ait El Cadi, University of Evora
9:55	HySelect project Kai Risthaus, DLR
10:10	Round-Table: Current CST funding frameworks, discussion on future funding requirements.
10:30	End of the workshop

CST4ALL team reserves the right to make changes to the workshop program

Funded by
the European Union

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CST4ALL Coordinator

Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

Projects contributing to this event

MSA-Trough (GA 101122276) Development of a parabolic Trough concentrator system for Molten Salt Application ([link](#))

ASTERIx-CAESar (GA 101122231) Air-Based Solar Thermal Electricity For Efficient Renewable Energy Integration & Compressed Air Energy Storage ([link](#))

Sun-to-Liquid II (GA 101122206) Integrated solar-thermochemical synthesis of liquid hydrocarbon fuels ([link](#))

SolarSC020L (GA 952953) SOLAR based sCO2 Operating Low-cost plants ([link](#))

SHARP-sCO2 (GA 101083899) Solar Hybrid Air-sCO2 Power Plants ([link](#))

SALTOPower (GA 101079303) European facility on Molten SALT technologies TO power and energy system applications ([link](#))

HySelect (GA 101101498) Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle ([link](#))

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